

FATIGUE DAMAGE RESPONSE OF CFRP WITH TOUGHENED MATRICES AND IMPROVED FIBRES

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ABSTRACT

Further improvements of carbon fibres towards fracture strains of about 2% make it necessary to use adapted matrix systems. In composites made from high strain fibres together with toughened matrix systems, pronounced improvements in the mechanical properties can be achieved. This is mainly due to the static strength, but under fatigue loading only small improvements in the behaviour are apparent. From the test results attained, it can be stated that in the design of a component, fatigue is of minor interest, but with the advent of improved and tougher composites fatigue will become more important in the future. During fatigue loading the damage progression was monitored, using stiffness reduction as a damage analogue. Parallel the development of transverse and longitudinal cracks were observed in the cross-ply laminates to enable a comparison of the damage behaviour. Additionally the variation of the electrical resistivity of the test specimen was continuously measured. It was possible to correlate this to the stiffness reduction and the corresponding fibre fracture.

INTRODUCTION

In the past years, manufacturers have sought to improve the mechanical properties of CFRP materials based on standard high strength carbon fibres by increasing the fracture strain of the fibres. In addition resin manufacturers have improved the composite matrix material with the principal aim of also increasing the fracture strain. The different fracture strains of the fibre and the matrix have a dominating influence on the mechanical behaviour of carbon fibre reinforced plastics [1]. At present most inves-

tigations are concentrated on conventional fibre/matrix systems, in which both components have similar values of fracture strains. However, to take better advantage of the composite, the design criteria for structures have to be shifted to higher values, allowing higher loads and strains in a component. One condition is to have tougher matrix systems to avoid early damage initiation [2-4]. The delay in crack initiation under static loading using tougher matrix systems has already been shown [5,6]. With the development of new high strain fibres with fracture strains up to 2% it becomes necessary to use improved matrix systems to fully realize the advantages of these fibres [6,7].

In the present paper mechanical properties and the damage progression during static and fatigue loading are reported for CFRP materials with both conventional and improved carbon fibres. They were combined with a conventional, brittle matrix and a modified toughened matrix system. Comparative studies were additionally performed on commercially available composites having tough matrix systems. To detect damage initiation and propagation during fatigue loading stiffness reduction was monitored as a damage analogue together with a measurement of the overall variation of the composite temperature [8] and the electrical resistivity [9].

EXPERIMENTAL

In the present investigation two epoxy resins of the Ciba Geigy company were used for a brittle standard resin system and a toughened resin system. The first matrix was a conventional, brittle resin Araldit MY720 (TGDDM) with the hardener HT976 (DDS) (weight ratio resin/hardener 100/47; fracture strain $\epsilon_f=1.9\%$). The second matrix, the toughened one, was a mixture of 50% Araldit MY720 and 50% Araldit LY556 (BPA-Epoxy) using the same hardener HT976 (weight ratio resins/hardener 100/41; fracture strain $\epsilon_f=4.25\%$).

These two matrices were used with two different high strength carbon fibres from the Toho Beslon company. The fibres had different fracture strains. The conventional fibre (HTA) had a fracture strain of about 1.4% and the new "high strain" fibre (ST 3) a strain of about 1.8%.

In addition to these model systems, which were laboratory made, two commercially available prepregs with toughened matrices were investigated: the thermoplast APC-2 ($\epsilon_f=35\%$) a polyetheretherketone (PEEK) from the ICI Petrochemicals and Plastics Division with the Hercules AS4 fibre and the epoxy R6376 ($\epsilon_f=3.1\%$) from the Ciba Geigy company with the Hercules IM6 fibre.

Two different laminates were selected for investigation:

1. Unidirectional, with eight plies, tested in the 0° and 90° direction
2. $[0_2, 90_2, 0_2, 90_2]_S$

The laminates were available in the form of large sheets. Test coupons were cut out in lengths of about 200mm with a width of 25mm. In all laminates with the epoxy matrix the alignment of the carbon fibres was satisfactory, whereas in the APC-2 laminates, where sheets from two different manufactures were used, the fibres showed up a wavy arrangement. In the sheets of one manufacturer the fibre waviness was concentrated on small areas having a short wavelength. In those from the other manufacturer, where only the cross-ply laminate was available, a long wavelength was present stretching over the entire specimen length.

Tensile tests and tension-tension fatigue tests with a R-value ($R = \sigma_{\min} / \sigma_{\max}$, σ_{\min} = minimum and σ_{\max} = maximum stress in each load cycle) of $R=0.1$ and a frequency of 10Hz were performed.

RESULTS

TENSILE TESTS

In TABLE 1 the fibre and neat resin properties are summarized. The results from the neat resins of the model systems are mean values from at least four tensile tests. All the other values including those of the fibres are taken from data sheets of the producers. The standard MY720 epoxy resin has the lowest fracture stress and fracture strain, while with the toughened resins the best values are achieved. The HTA and ST 3 fibres have the same Young's modulus but different fracture strains and fracture stresses.

TABLE 1
Mechanical properties of carbon fibres and neat resins

	Matrices				Fibres			
	MY720	MY720/LY556	R6376	APC-2	HTA*	ST 3*	AS4*	IM6*
Fracture Stress σ_f [MPa]	61	93	105	100	3400	4300	3600	4100
Young's Modulus E [GPa]	3.3	2.2	3.6	1.7	238	238	235	281
Fracture Strain ϵ_f [%]	1.87	4.25	3.1	≈35	1.4	1.8	1.5	1.5

* from Data Sheet

The AS4 fibre has similar properties as the HTA fibre, while the IM6 fibre, an intermediate modulus fibre, attains the same fracture strain as the AS4 fibre but has a higher Young's modulus and fracture stress.

Figure 1. Mechanical properties of the investigated laminates

The behaviour of the constituents considerably influence the mechanical properties of fibre reinforced composites. In Fig.1 the unidirectional laminate properties are shown, tested either in fibre direction $[0_g]$ or perpendicular $[90_g]$ to it, in comparison to the tensile test properties of the cross-ply laminates. Comparing the results of Fig.1a with the values of TABLE 1, it turns out, that the neat resins have a considerably higher fracture stress than the $[90_g]$ specimen. In addition the fracture strain is drastically reduced (Fig.1b). The Young's modulus for all the resin systems also increases in a transverse tensile test (Fig.1c). The two commercial products have a higher fracture stress and strain than the model systems. This is especially pronounced for the APC-2, but it has the lowest Young's modulus. The better values attained with the neat resin compared to the transverse test results are to be expected, taking into consideration that the likelihood of failure on the fibre/matrix interface is due to a weak bonding between fibre and matrix, which makes a transverse tensile test an effective tool in determining bond quality. The bond quality between the epoxy matrix and the carbon fibres has been found to be rather poor. For the APC-2 a better bond quality has been found. Not only a weak bonding between fibre and matrix favours interfacial fracture in a tensile test specimen, but also the stress concentration caused by tension perpendicular to the fibre $[10]$. The maximum normal stress can be expected in the fibre matrix interface and exceeds $1.5\sigma_x$, when σ_x is the normal stress applied to the composite. The transverse composite stiffness is not remarkably different for the epoxy matrix materials, indicating that the transverse stiffness is strongly influenced by the volume element of carbon fibres and less by the stiffness of the matrix material. However, the low increase in composite transverse stiffness has to be weighed against the corresponding increase in local stress concentration during loading, which indicates the decrease in the composite strength when compared to the neat resin. Local yielding or viscoelastic behaviour of the matrix materials will relieve the stress concentration somewhat, which is particularly true for the APC-2 material. Testing the unidirectional laminates in the 0° direction, it turns out that a tougher matrix system increases the strain to failure (compare the model systems in Fig.1b). Using a high strain fibre gives further improvement. The commercial product (R6376/IM6) surpasses all the other systems, having a fracture strain of about the same as the pure fibre, a result which is not fully attained from the model systems. However, the fracture strain of the APC-2 is not as high as it could be expected from the constituent properties. The pronounced reduction in the properties seems to be strongly dependent on the wavy arrangement of the fibres, which is observed in certain areas of the specimens and at which failure always occurs.

The cross-ply $[0_2, 90_2, 0_2, 90_2]_s$ laminates show the same tendency as the unidirectional laminates: an increase in fracture strength with increasing

matrix toughness and fracture strain of the fibres. The commercial epoxy based laminate R6376/IM6 again attains good results when compared to the model systems. The APC-2/AS4 laminate with the short wavelength of the 0°-fibres again attained only low values. In the second quality the 0°-fibres were arranged so that they had a long wavelength. The resulting data were now in that range as could be expected from the constituent properties.

Transverse crack development was determined in situ during the static tests. In tougher matrix systems less transverse cracks appeared in the 90°-plies (Fig.2). Also the onset of the first transverse cracks was shifted to higher strain values when a tougher matrix was used.

Figure 2. Number of transverse ply cracks versus static tensile strain

FATIGUE TESTS

Tension-tension fatigue tests were performed on cross-ply laminates of the different composites investigated. In Fig.3 the normalized stiffness versus the number of load cycles is plotted. The behaviour of the material with the ST 3 fibre in combination with the two different model matrix systems is shown for a maximum stress level of $\sigma_{\max} = 800\text{MPa}$. It is clearly to be seen, that with the tougher matrix system a higher fatigue life can be attained. From the commercial products the R6376/IM6 exceeded at this load level more than 7×10^6 cycles without failure. However, the APC-2/AS4 with the long wavelength arrangement of the fibres, failed after about $N=450$ cycles. The first quality failed to attain the first load cycle for that stress level.

Figure 3. Normalized stiffness versus the number of load cycles for the ST 3 fibre in combination with a brittle (MY720) and a tough (MY720/LY556) matrix.

Stiffness reduction can be used as a damage analogue. Three different ranges can be distinguished in the stiffness reduction curve [11]. At the beginning of fatigue loading a first range with a pronounced stiffness reduction, which can be related to transverse crack development in the 90° plies, is visible (compare Fig.4). A saturation in the number of transverse cracks will be attained. Further fatigue loading leads to a second range with a small nearly linear decrease in stiffness.

Figure 4. Stiffness reduction and transverse and longitudinal crack development for a cross-ply laminate

Within this range of fatigue, longitudinal cracks along 0° fibres in the load bearing plies develop additionally and no saturation stage will be attained, what additionally Figure 4 shows. At intersections of longitudinal and transverse cracks internal delaminations initiate. In the third range, the increasing number of fibre fractures lead to a decrease in stiffness. Just

prior to failure, in the very last load cycles the stiffness decreases dramatically. This stiffness reduction is associated with the fracture not only of single fibres but of whole fibre bundles. The temperature variation of a test coupon can equally be used to monitor damage [8].

During fatigue loading a variation of the electrical resistivity can be registered. The electrical resistivity is dependent on the conductivity of the carbon fibres and its change can therefore be related to fibre fracture [9]. Fig.5 shows, that stiffness reduction, which is associated to damage, occurs when a stepwise increase in the electrical resistivity is measured.

Figure 5. Variation of the electrical resistivity, specimen temperature and stiffness due to fatigue loading of a cross-ply laminate.

The use of tougher matrix systems has an considerable influence on the damage development in fatigue. Fatigue tests were performed on all six materials with an equal maximum stress per cycle of $\sigma_{max}=750\text{MPa}$. For each material three test coupons were tested. The tests were continued up to $N=100, N=10,000$ and $N=100,000$ load cycles, respectively followed by penetrant enhanced X-ray radiography. Comparing the radiographs of all materials (Fig.6), it turns out that using a tougher matrix and improved fibres considerably delays the formation of longitudinal and transverse cracks. Using the brittle MY720 matrix in combination with the HTA fibre, failure occurs before 10,000 load cycles were completed. Also the APC-2/AS4 which was tested in the second quality (long wavelength) did not complete 10,000 load cycles. However, this result was not influenced by any regular damage pattern from fabrication flaws, such as the wavy arrangement of the fibres, because very few transverse and longitudinal cracks could be observed in the specimen. Damage was concentrated in the vicinity of the final crack. The best results were attained with the commercial R6376/IM6 system. Here comparatively few cracks had developed after the same number of load cycles at the same stress level as the model systems.

MY720 / HTA

$N_f = 3370$ Cyc.

MY720 / ST 3

MY720 / LY556 / HTA

MY720 / LY556 / ST 3

R6376 / IM6

APC-2 / AS4*

$N_f = 790$ Cyc.

5mm

N = 100 Cyc.

N = 10,000 Cyc.

N = 100,000 Cyc.

* Long Wavelength of 0°-Fibres

Figure 6. Damage development during fatigue loading of cross-ply laminates, $\sigma_{max} = 750$ MPa, $R = 0.1$, $f = 10$ Hz.

Figure 7. Fatigue behaviour of the brittle (MY720/HTA) and the tough (MY720/LY556/ST 3) model system.

The improvements attained in the static tensile data, when using toughened matrices and fibres with a high strain to failure are not of the same range order under tension fatigue. In Fig.7 the variation of peak stress σ_{max} versus the number of load cycles to failure N_f for the brittle and the tough model system is plotted. Additionally included are mean values of at least four tensile tests together with the scatter of the test data. The tough material can endure the highest number of load cycles at the highest stress levels, but the Wöhler-curve is considerably steeper than the curve of the brittle material. Also the difference between the tensile test data and the fatigue data are higher for the toughened material.

Fatigue is actually not a critical design criteria for CFRP, but it can become more important if the more fatigue-sensitive, toughened matrix systems are used and if the static design limitations are extended.

CONCLUSION

It was possible to show that using toughened matrix systems and fibres with a higher strain to failure improves static and fatigue properties of CFRP. This can be attributed to the fact that the development of transverse and longitudinal cracks is delayed and shifted to higher load levels. Also the damage mechanisms, which initiate final failure are delayed in fatigue tests. But the results of the fatigue tests using the tougher materials were not as good as expected according to the tensile test results. That means, that for using the advanced newer materials in an aeroplane structure a design criteria based on static tests might not be sufficient. Fatigue behaviour may become more important in future, when the design criteria is extended.

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